

Magnetic Properties of Complex Compounds and their Electronic Constitution.

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Of recent years many attempts have been made to correlate the magnetic properties and the electronic constitution of complex inorganic compounds. Of these mention may be made of those by Cabrera (*J. Phys. Radium*, 1925, **6**, 276) supported by Jackson (*Phil. Mag.*, 1926, **2**, 87 ; 1927, (vii) **4**, 1070), Welo and Baudisch (*Nature*, 1925, **116**, 606), Bose (*Zeit. Phys.*, 1925, **35**, 213, 219), Lessheim, Meyer and Samuel (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, **165**, 253) and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 73). A critical examination of all these views from chemical standpoint has been made by one of us Ray (*loc. cit.*). In order to further test the validity of these different views we undertook the measurement of magnetic susceptibilities of a variety of complex compounds, the results of which are embodied in the present paper and form the basis of discussion raised herein. We will however pass over Lessheim and his co-workers' view as it could not be reconciled with our present conception of valency. This has already been pointed out by Ray (*loc. cit.*).

Both Welo-Baudisch and Bose assume that the magnetic properties depend primarily on the "effective atomic number" of the central atom of the complex ion as defined and interpreted by Sidgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 725). They have also adduced some evidences in support of their views. According to these views a complex becomes diamagnetic when its effective atomic number is equal to the atomic number of an inert gas ; and when this number for the complex differs from that of the next inert gas by n units, the complex becomes paramagnetic with a magnetic moment corresponding to n Bohr magnetons (Bose, *loc. cit.*). But this rule does not hold good in the case of complex ions formed by zinc and cobaltous cobalt. Welo and Baudisch do not give any definite distribution of electrons in different sub-groups giving rise to co-ordination bonds ; whereas Bose has given a scheme for the same which however fails to account for all the chemical properties of the complex

as has already been pointed out by Rây (*loc. cit.*). Cabrera assumes that co-ordinating electrons are arranged in two groups of 4 or 6 each depending on the nature of the co-ordination in an external quantum group and they contribute nothing to the magnetic moment. It is further implied in Cabrera's scheme that paramagnetism in complex ions develops when any sub-group in the main quantum group of the central atom does not contain its full quota of electrons; consequently a completed or vacant sub-group develops diamagnetic property. Rây also holds the same view which was first formulated by Ladenburg (*Naturwiss.* 1920, 8, 6); but Rây has distinguished two types of complexes, penetration or perfect and associated or imperfect complexes depending on the nature of their electronic configuration. However, both Cabrera and Rây do not stick to any definite rule regarding the magnetic moments of paramagnetic complexes as enunciated by Bose.

We shall now proceed to discuss the results of our measurements of magnetic susceptibilities of a variety of complex compounds on the basis of these four different views in order to determine which of them best explains the experimental values. The measurements were all made in the solid state by means of a Curie's balance with conductivity water as the standard and at the room temperature (25-34°). The specific or mass susceptibility of water is taken as $\chi_m = -0.72 \times 10^{-6}$.

As our object was to determine the nearest Bohr magneton value for the paramagnetic complexes and also the magnetic nature of the complex itself (dia- or para-magnetic) we did not take sufficient pains to obtain magnetically pure (apart from chemically pure) samples in all cases, specially in the case of certain unstable compounds as will be indicated later on. So in those cases our experimental results should be regarded as giving more or less approximate values and consequently we do not claim any high degree of accuracy for them.

Further, in calculating the magneton number we have ignored the effect of diamagnetic atoms and ions, as they have already been found by Rosenbohm (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1919, 93, 693) to exert negligible influence so far as our present purpose is concerned.

The results of measurements are given in the accompanying table.

Results of susceptibility measurements.

No.	Substance.	Temperature (Centigrade.)	$\chi_m \cdot 10^6$	${}^7\mu_{\text{Weiss}}$	${}^7\mu_{\text{Bohr}}$ (nearest)	${}^7\mu_{\text{Bohr}}$ (theoretical, calc. after Welo and Bose's rule).
1.	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	25°	48.7	23.6	4	3
2.	$\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	27°	37.0	22.9	4	3
3.	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	26°	35.9	23.0	4	1
4.	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	26°	33.6	20.9	3.4	3
5.	$\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	25°	33.2	21.7	3.4	3
6.	$\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}$	26°	18.6	23.2	4	3
7.	$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	26°	18.1	14.4	2	2
8.	$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	26°	13.9	13.6	2	2
9.	$\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	27°	14.8	14.5	2	2
10.	$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	25°	16.2	14.3	2	2
11.	$\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	27°	11.6	13.2	2	2
12.	$\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	26°	57.7	23.4	4	4
13.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2$ (Nickel dimethylglyoxime)	27°	0.10	1.8	...	2
14.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{ON}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Nickel dicyandiamidine)	...	-0.32	...	Dia	2
15.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2)$ (Nickel rubeanate, Rây and Ray, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1926, 3, 118).	29°	0.28	1.7	...	2
16.	$\text{K}_2\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	...	-0.362	}	Dia Dia	2
		...	-0.57(B)			
17.	$\text{K}_2\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4$	...	-0.261	}	Dia Dia	2
		...	-0.49(B)			
18.	$\left[\text{Co} \begin{array}{c} (\text{NH}_3)_5 \\ (\text{NO}) \\ \text{(black)} \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}_2$	29°	13.3	13.9	2	2
19.	$\left[\text{Co} \begin{array}{c} (\text{NH}_3)_5 \\ (\text{NO}) \\ \text{(red)} \end{array} \right] (\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$	...	-0.109	Dia	Dia	Dia
20.	$\text{K} \left[\text{Fe} \begin{array}{c} (\text{NO})_2 \\ \text{S}_2\text{O}_8 \end{array} \right] \text{H}_2\text{O}$	30°	0.0245	0.6	...	...

No.	Substance.	Temperature (Centigrade)	$\chi \times 10^3$	η Weiss	η Bohr (nearest)	η Bohr (Theoretical, calc. after Welo and Bose's rule).
21.	$K_2Fe_3(NO)_{11}S_6 \cdot 2H_2O$	28°	0.159	1.2	...	...
22.	$KFe(NO)_5 \cdot 3H_2O$	25°	0.54	2.8	...	...
23.	$Na_2 \left[Fe \begin{matrix} (NO) \\ (CN)_4 \end{matrix} \right] 2H_2O$	...	-0.31 -0.35 (Welo, loc. cit)	Dia	Dia	Dia
24.	$K_2 \left[Co \begin{matrix} S_2O_3 \\ (CN)_5 \end{matrix} \right]$	...	-0.362	"	"	"
25.	$(NH_4)_4 \left[Co \begin{matrix} S_2O_3 \\ (CN)_5 \end{matrix} \right]$	...	-0.372	"	"	"
26.	$Rb_2 \left[Co \begin{matrix} S_2O_3 \\ (CN)_6 \end{matrix} \right]$	...	-0.546	"	"	"
27.	$Cs_2 \left[Co \begin{matrix} S_2O_3 \\ (CN)_6 \end{matrix} \right]$	...	-0.299	"	"	"
28.	$Na_4 \left[Co \begin{matrix} S_2O_3 \\ (CN)_5 \end{matrix} \right] H_2O$	...	-0.303	"	"	"
29.	$Tl_2 \left[Co \begin{matrix} S_2O_3 \\ (CN)_5 \end{matrix} \right]$	...	-0.181	"	"	"
30.	$\left[Co \begin{matrix} S_2O_3 \\ (NH_3)_5 \end{matrix} \right] Cl$	...	-0.291	"	"	"
31.	$K_3Co(CN)_6$	...	-0.320 -0.37(B)	} "	"	"
32.	$K_4Co(CN)_6$	...	-0.398	"	"	1
33.	$K_6 \left[Co_3 \begin{matrix} SO_3 \\ (CN)_{10} \end{matrix} \right]$	...	-0.407	"	"	Dia
34.	$Co(C_2S_2N_4H_2) \cdot 2H_2O$	3.1	15.6	14.1	2	3
35.	$K_4Mn(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$	23°	4.1	10	1	1
36.	$K_3Mn(CN)_6$	25°	10.8 16.7(B)	} 14.5 } 18(B)	} 2 } 3(B)	} 2
37.	$Cu(C_2H_5ON)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ Copper dicyandiamidoe	29°	3.3	7.9	1	1
38.	$Cu(C_2NO_2H_4)_2 \cdot H_2O$ Copper aminoacetate.	28°	5.1	8.3	1	1

No.	Substance.	Temperature (Centigrade).	$\chi_m \cdot 10^4$	${}^7\text{Weiss}$	${}^7\text{Bohr}$ (nearest)	${}^7\text{Bohr}$ (Theoretical, calc. after Welo and Bose's rule).
39.	$\text{KCu}(\text{CN})_2$	...	-0.287	Dia	Dia	...
40.	$\text{K}_2\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	30°	11.4	16.5 (?)	2	2
41.	$\text{K}_2\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$	26°	15.5 20(B)	17.2 19(B)	3 3(B)	3
42.	$\text{K}_2\text{MoCl}_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	26°	13.1	17.6	3	3
43.	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Mo}(\text{SCN})_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	26°	9.5	17.8	3	3
44.	$\text{K}_2\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	...	-0.295 -0.48(B) (anhydrous)	Dia	Dia	Dia
45.	$\text{K}_2\text{W}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}_5$	31°	4.0	8.6	1	4
46.	$\text{K}_2\text{W}_2\text{Cl}_7$	...	-0.265	Dia	Dia	...
47.	$\text{K}_2\text{W}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	...	-0.36 -0.43(B) (anhydrous)	Dia	Dia	Dia

where χ_m = mass susceptibility; ${}^7\text{Weiss}$ = Weiss magneton number and ${}^7\text{Bohr}$ = Bohr's magneton number.

Since this paper was communicated a paper by Biltz (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 170, 161) reached us here; in this paper he has also given the results of susceptibility measurements of a few of the above compounds. His values though slightly differing from ours are quite comparable for our present purposes except in the case of the compound No. 36, where a serious and large discrepancy is noted. But in this latter case we have no reasons to doubt our own value. His values are indicated in the table by the symbol B.

Of the six cobaltous complexes examined (nos. 1—6 *cf.* Table) four give values almost equal to 4 Bohr magnetons. One of these four is a sixfold and the other three are fourfold co-ordination complexes. The magnetic moment of these complexes approaches the value (${}^7\text{Weiss} = 24.56$) for the simple cobaltous salts. The remaining two give values between 3 to 4 Bohr magnetons.

Cobaltous complexes are regarded by Rây only as associated complexes wherein the distribution of electrons in the simple cobaltous ion is left unchanged. As for the other two compounds nos. 4 and 5 it may be assumed that we are dealing here with mixtures

in which a small proportion has the tendency to assume a more perfect type resembling Rây's penetration complexes which leads to a rearrangement of electrons reducing the magnetic moment to a certain extent.

Of the five nickel complexes examined (nos. 7—11), all give values approximately equal to 2 Bohr magnetons, but always slightly lower than the value for the simple nickel ion which is equal to 16—17 Weiss magnetons. The compound no. 12 which is a ferrous complex of the associated type gives a value almost equal to 4 Bohr magnetons which is only slightly lower than that for the simple ferrous salts (26.0 Weiss). The slight excess of the magneton values in the case of both the simple nickelous and ferrous salts over the integral Bohr magneton values may be explained as due to their containing mixtures of isomeric ions caused by a difference in the arrangement of outer electrons in the M_3 level of the atom.

Of the five nickel complexes of the fourfold type (nos. 13—17), only the compounds nickel dimethyl glyoxime and nickel rubeanate possess a very small residual paramagnetism amounting approximately to only one Weiss magneton. So, for our present purpose they may be regarded as practically diamagnetic. Potassium nickelocyanide both in the hydrated and anhydrous conditions are diamagnetic. The magnetic properties of sodium and potassium nickelocyanides were also studied by Depold (*vide* Jackson, *Phil. Mag.*, 1927, 4, 1073) who also found them to be diamagnetic. These results cannot in any way be explained by Welo and Baudisch's and by Bose's views. Cabrera's view also fails to account for such anomalous results. In order to explain the diamagnetic character of sodium and potassium nickelocyanides on the basis of Cabrera's view, Jackson (*loc. cit.*) however suggests that in their cases a rearrangement of electrons in the nickel ion takes place. But what is the reason for such rearrangement and why does such rearrangement take place in only a few nickel complexes have not been stated. According to Rây's view we may regard that the nickelous ion can form both association and penetration complexes depending on the nature of the co-ordinating groups. With strongly polar groups or ions, it may reasonably be assumed that nickel can form perfect or penetration complexes, though usually it forms association complexes. The diamagnetic character of the above nickel

compounds may be ascribed to the formation of such perfect complexes. The electronic configuration for such a perfect complex may be represented by the following scheme :

Ni ⁺⁺ complex, perfect type (fourfold)	Electrons in K _{1,1} to M _{2,2} levels.	M _{3,3}	M _{3,3}	N _{1,1}	N _{2,2} , N _{3,3}
	18	4	6	...	6

Every four of six electrons in M_{3,3} and N_{2,2} levels are coupled and form the co-ordination bonds. Such configuration would evidently give rise to diamagnetic property.

It also incidentally confirms the complex character of nickel rubeanate as was established by Rây and Ray (*loc. cit.*) from a study of its chemical and other physical properties

Of the five nitroso compounds examined (nos. 18—23) nos. 18 and 22 which are rather unstable were evidently not in a magnetically pure condition. The values observed should therefore be regarded only as approximate ones. The object of these measurements is to determine the behaviour of the -NO group in the complex. According to Sidgwick an -NO group inside the complex furnishes three electrons to the central atom, one by transfer and two by sharing. Besides, the idea that the NO molecule can part with three electrons is supported by the theory of the nature of non-polar molecules as deduced from band spectra (*cf.* Johnson, *Sci. Progress*, Oct. 1927, p. 246), according to which the structure of NO molecule is similar to that of aluminium containing three valence electrons outside the L-shell. The diamagnetism of sodium nitroprusside, a ferric complex, has been explained on this basis. The black compound no. 18 can be represented as

where the cobalt atom has been proved to behave as bivalent (*cf.* Werner and Karrer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1918, 1, 54). The observed susceptibility of the compound agrees however with that demanded by Bose's rule.

It is well known that the black variety is unstable and passes into the red modification. The red variety of the nitrate is represented

by the formula $[(\text{NH}_3)_5 \text{Co}-\text{N}_2\text{O}_2-\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5] (\text{NO}_2)_4$ and the cobalt atom is regarded as trivalent; the group N_2O_2 behaving as a residue of hyponitrous acid (*cf.* Werner and Karrer, *loc. cit.*). Assuming the red compound to be a cobaltic complex and the bivalent acid radicle N_2O_2 to furnish one electron to each cobalt atom to form one co-ordination bond in each case, the effective atomic number of each cobalt atom in the complex becomes equal to 36, the number for the inert gas krypton and thus makes it diamagnetic.

It is however difficult to explain the value of the magnetic moment for the black modification of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 5\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{NO}$ according to Cabrera's and Rây's schemes. But as this compound is rather very unstable it seems that it is a mixture of two different forms with the cobalt atom in two different states of oxidation,—that is a mixture of an associated cobaltous complex with a perfect cobaltic complex, and the magnetic moment consequently lies between the values characteristic for the two. Still however, the magnetic moment corresponding to exactly two Bohr magnetons is significant.

The compounds nos. 20, 21 and 22 have a small paramagnetic moment ranging from 0.6 to 3 Weiss magnetons approximately. The constitution of these compounds are still obscure, specially the valency of iron. So it is very difficult to ascribe any electronic configuration to the co-ordinating iron atom or to determine the function of the $-\text{NO}$ group. It can however be stated with reason from the very low values of their magnetic moments approximating to zero that they are more or less perfect type of complexes.

The compounds nos. 25 to 29 were lent to us by Rây and Moulik. The compound no. 31, potassium cobalticyanide could not be freed from traces of iron most probably present as potassium ferricyanide which is isomorphous with the cobalticyanide. Even starting with Merck's reagent cobaltnitrate, precipitating any trace of iron by means of ammonium chloride and ammonia, and then treating the filtrate with the purest sodium bicarbonate for the production of iron-free cobalt carbonate which was then treated with Merck's reagent potassium cyanide free from ferrocyanide, etc., and recrystallising the cobalticyanide obtained several times from conductivity water we found that the product still contained slight traces of iron. We have not as yet been able to trace the source of this iron. Probably it has been absorbed from the floating dust in the laboratory atmosphere. However the value of

the diamagnetic susceptibility given here represents the concordant result of three different preparations of the compound. We can therefore reasonably believe that when obtained absolutely pure it will manifest a little higher diamagnetic susceptibility. Incidentally it indicates the difficulty of obtaining magnetically pure samples for which simple chemical analysis is no sure guide.

All the complex cobaltic compounds from nos. 24 to 31 are, as usual, diamagnetic. All the four views discussed above lead to the same result. A striking result has however been obtained with potassium cobaltocyanide (no. 32). This compound which is rather unstable has been found to give a diamagnetic susceptibility. Though the value of the susceptibility given above should be regarded as an approximate one on account of the instability of the compound which does not therefore permit of further purification, it can be definitely asserted that the compound is diamagnetic. Because paramagnetic property of any compound cannot be masked by the presence of a fairly large amount of diamagnetic impurities. According to Bose's and Welo's views potassium cobaltocyanide should give a magnetic moment equal to one Bohr magneton. Thus these views fail to explain its diamagnetic character. Cabrera's view is also incapable of explaining this anomalous result. Ráy has however suggested in his paper (*loc. cit.*) that the last electron in potassium cobaltocyanide behaves as a valence electron and is pushed outside the level of the co-ordinating electrons. So under these circumstances the complex should behave magnetically similar to rubidium atom of atomic number 37. The mass susceptibility of Rb atom is quite small verging practically to diamagnetism; the values for the mass and atomic susceptibilities of rubidium are 0.07×10^{-6} and 5.97×10^{-6} respectively (*cf.* Honda and Owen's Table in "Magnetism and Atomic Structure" by Stoner, p. 138). The Weiss magneton number for Rb atom is therefore practically negligible being approximately equal to 0.2 only. Hence it is not unreasonable to assume that potassium cobaltocyanide in a crystalline condition will exhibit diamagnetism. But it appears to us that a more probable explanation of the diamagnetism of potassium cobaltocyanide is this. In this complex we may regard one of the cyanogen ions to be linked by one electron only which it supplies to the central cobalt atom instead of a pair of electrons as usual. This produces an unstable condition impelling the central atom to readily lose one more electron resulting in the change of

the one electron bond into a two-electron co-ordinate bond, and the cobaltocyanide is oxidised to cobalticyanide—both the electrons being apparently supplied by the cyanogen group under consideration. On this assumption the magnetic behaviour of potassium cobaltocyanide as experimentally observed falls in a line with the views of Bose, Welo and Rây, though it is difficult to be represented by Cabrera's scheme. The high value of its diamagnetic susceptibility—higher than that of the very stable and perfect complex potassium cobalticyanide is certainly due to contamination with diamagnetic substances such as potassium cyanide, alcohol and ether. The substance was washed with alcohol and ether to avoid decomposition by water and could not be thoroughly dried for the same reason.

The compound no. 33 recently prepared by one of us (Rây) is a binuclear cobalt complex and is represented by the following formula by its author:—

In common with all the sixfold perfect cobaltic complex this compound exhibits diamagnetism.

The compound no. 34 (cobalt rubeanate) furnishes another instance of anomalous magnetic behaviour. This compound was represented by its author (Rây and Ray, *loc. cit.*) as an inner-metallic cobaltous complex. It ought to give, according to Bose's rule, a magnetic moment of 3 Bohr magnetons. But it actually gives only 2 Bohr magnetons. Both Rây's and Cabrera's views which do not predict any definite quantitative measure of the magnetic moment, can however give electronic configurations for this compound. But it seems that the chemical constitution of the compound itself is not quite clear. Rây and Ray have already noticed that the two water molecules present in the compound are not expelled even by heating to 130°. This suggests that the water molecules possibly form a part of the complex giving a sixfold instead of a fourfold complex. In any way the compound can reasonably be regarded as a mixture of two or more forms. That it approaches more or less a perfect complex is proved by the fact of its having a magneton number two Bohr units less than that of a simple cobaltous salt.

Compounds nos. 35 and 36 are the two complex mangano- and mangani-cyanides of potassium. Their susceptibilities are in conformity with the requirements of Bose's rule. According to Rây's view of the structure of sixfold complexes the electronic configurations for the two manganese complexes are given by the following scheme :

Substance.	Electrons in $K_{1,1}$ to $M_{2,2}$ levels.	$M_{2,2}$	$M_{3,3}$	$N_{1,1}$	N_2
$K_2 Mn(CN)_6$	18	4	6	1	6
$K_2 Mn(CN)_5$	18	3	6	1	6

Compounds nos. 37 and 38 should be regarded as Rây's association complexes, their magnetic moments remaining the same as for simple cupric salts. Compound no. 39 being a cuprous salt should be evidently diamagnetic.

Chromocyanide (no. 40) gives a value slightly higher than what conforms to Bose's rule. But as the compound is extremely unstable readily changing into chromicyanide specially at a temperature like 30°C (the laboratory temperature at the time of measurements), the observed value cannot represent the true magnetic moment of the compound in question.

The molybdenum compounds nos. 42 and 43 with the central atom of molybdenum in the trivalent condition behave like chromium complexes and like the latter obey Bose's rule. The compound no. 44, octacyano-potassium molybdenate with quadrivalent molybdenum as the central atom is diamagnetic as is to be expected, since being an eightfold complex its effective atomic number is equal to 54, the number for the inert gas xenon.

The tungsten compound no. 47 behaves exactly like the corresponding molybdenum compound. The effective atomic number of the central quadrivalent tungsten here is equal to 86, the number for the inert gas emanation or niton.

The tungsten compounds nos. 45 and 46 however give anomalous results. The compound $K_3 W_2 Cl_6$ is diamagnetic. In this the tungsten atom is trivalent. It is very difficult to explain its diamagnetic character on the basis of any of the views under discussion, as its constitution is obscure. Possibly in this case there is a direct linkage between the two tungsten atoms which give rise to complications. Again the compound $K_2 W(CH)_2 Cl_4$ exhibits a magnetic moment of one Bohr magneton. The tungsten atom is tetravalent here ; but it is very difficult to represent such a complex as having a magnetic moment of one Bohr magneton on any of the views under discussion.

The effective atomic number in this case is $74-4+12=82$. This is a solitary case in which an even number of electrons gives an odd value of magneton number on the Bohr scale, and there is no reason to assume any of the co-ordination bonds as arising from the sharing of one electron only.

As a result of the above discussion of the values of magnetic moment of a variety of complex compounds communicated in this paper, it may be observed that Welo's and Bose's rules which claim to give a quantitative measure of the magnetic moment of a complex in terms of Bohr magneton number fail altogether in many well-known cases. It has also been found that Cabrera's scheme as well cannot account for the magnetic behaviour of a few well-defined complexes. On the whole Rây's view appears to explain satisfactorily the magnetic character of the largest number of complex compounds dealt with in this discussion. It is however noteworthy that whereas Bose enunciated his rule from a study of the magnetic properties of the complex compounds as far as investigated at the time, the rule, in spite of its failure in the cases of association complexes of cobalt and perfect complexes of nickel, has been evidently extended to the cases of nitroso-compounds of cobalt and cyanogen complexes of manganese. Finally, in view of the possibility of existence of different types of complexes as also their isomeric mixtures in a particular compound, an integral value of Bohr's magneton number cannot be always attributed to them.

Carbonyls of metallic elements *e.g.* $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$, $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$, $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$ and $\text{Mo}(\text{CO})_6$ present some interesting features. Nickel, iron and chromium carbonyls have been found to be diamagnetic. The character of molybdenum compound is not yet known. The effective atomic number of these carbonyl compounds being equal to the atomic number of the next inert gas, they should be diamagnetic according to Welo's and Bose's views. And their actual diamagnetic character is regarded as a strong evidence in support of their views. But it should be pointed out, as Jackson has done (*Phil. Mag.*, 1927, 4, 1070), that in their representation of the configurations of these carbonyls they have assumed that each carbonyl group is co-ordinatively linked by a pair of shared electrons supplied by it to the central metallic atom. This however does not take into account the valence condition of the central atom. In other words the central atom is supposed to exercise its co-ordinating valency without exhibiting any of its normal or primary valency.

This is rather unusual and contradictory to Werner's co-ordination theory of valency. Jackson has therefore represented them in a different way so that the valence condition of the central atom may also be easily recognised; and he has tried to explain their diamagnetic character by attributing to them electronic configurations based on Cabrera's scheme. The compound nickel carbonyl is represented by him as $[\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_5]\text{CO}$ and the iron carbonyl as $[\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4]\text{CO}$. This sort of representation is not quite satisfactory as it makes the carbonyl compounds electrolytes with a bivalent complex positive ion and a bivalent negative CO' ion for which there is absolutely no justification or evidence; besides, the co-ordination value for the nickel atom is reduced to three which is also unusual. A more satisfactory explanation on the basis of Ray's view can here be offered. It is well known that there are many co-ordination compounds in which inspite of the manifestation of the primary valency of the central atom, the compound as a whole is non-electrolyte. Instances of this type are furnished by trinitro-triammine cobalt $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{NO}_2)_3]$, tetrachloro-diammine platinum $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_4]$, trithiocyanato triammine chromium $[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{SCN})_3]$ trichloro-triammine iridium $[\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}_3]$ etc. In these the atoms or groups like Cl, NO_2 , SCN, etc. satisfying the primary valencies of the central atom are linked to the latter by non-ionizable or co-valent bonds, and are situated along with the co-ordinatively bound molecules in the same primary sphere of the central atom. In exactly the same way one or two of the CO groups in the carbonyl compounds may be regarded as bound to the central atom by co-valent bonds satisfying the normal or principal valencies of the central atom. Thus if we assume that the metallic atoms in their carbonyl compounds exert their lowest possible normal valency *i.e.*, two in these cases, we can easily arrive at the following electronic configurations for them.

Substance.	Electrons in $\text{K}_{1,1}$ to $\text{M}_{2,2}$	$\text{M}_{3,2}$	$\text{M}_{3,3}$	$\text{N}_{1,1}$	$\text{N}_{2,1}$	$\text{N}_{2,2}$	Total electrons.
1. $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_5$	18	4	6		6		34
2. $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$	18	4	6	2	6		36
3. $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$	18	4	6		6		34

It is not difficult to make assumptions regarding the locations of these 4, 4 or 6, 6 groups.

It may not be out of place here to point out that the ordinary conductivity water is not a sufficiently sure standard for susceptibility measurements; and we had to further purify this water by fractional solidification till a constant mass deflection in the Curie balance was obtained.

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P.S.—In a paper recently published in the *Phil. Mag.* (1928, 6, 1046) and received here since the communication of the present paper, Bose has further developed his theory on a theoretical basis in which he has assumed as Rây has already done that in the case of cobaltous and nickleous complexes the co-ordinating electrons lie outside the M-shell.

